

The Importance of Neuro Linguistic Programming Skills as a Communication Tool in the Workplace

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Abstract

Purpose: The present study aims to investigate the importance of neuro linguistic programming skills as a communication tool in the workplace. **Methodology:** The qualitative exploratory study was conducted. In the data-collection stage, qualitative data was collected via (reviewing literature and conducted semi- structured interviews with experts in neuro- linguistic programming world- wide, who have business background). **Findings:** The present research results showed that, neuro linguistic programming skills as a communication tool are very important in the business context. In addition, the most important skills that management and employees can use are: representation system, predicates, meta modal, anchoring, leading and pacing, sensory acuity, building rapport, understanding strategies of others, as they are used externally - communicating with others in the workplace and communicating internally - within ourselves. Furthermore, these skills promote communication in the workplace via applying communication mechanisms through the building of familiarity and ways of persuasion in understanding the strategies and ways of thinking of others and the quality of their personalities. Moreover, neuro linguistic programming skills improve the external communication with others in the workplace to a very large extent, using all the different communication mechanisms, such as: understanding the ways of thinking of the other, the hidden meaning behind his/her words and his/her actions, and also to achieve common goals in the work place. Finally, Companies that use neuro linguistic programming skills in communicating with customers, achieve greater profits and excellent customer service. **Originality;Value:** The current research contributes to the literature of organization behavior, as follows; First; the current research enriches the literature by adding a brick to the foundation of organizational cognitive neuroscience that is established by the previous researchers in the area of organization behavior by merging two different sciences: Neuropsychology science and management science which is represented by organizational behavior, and formulate new science which is called organizational cognitive neuroscience. Furthermore, the research adds to the active debate on the importance/ applicability of Neuro linguistic programming skills as a communication tool in the workplace.

Keywords: Neuro Linguistic Programming skills, Organization Behavior, Organization Cognitive Neuroscience, Egypt

1. Introduction

The history of management science has witnessed integrating management with various science, such as: engineering,

mathematics, biology, psychology, sociology, neuroscience. According to “Frederic Taylor (1856–1915)” the father

of scientific management theory, he was an engineer who founded theory that merged between engineering and management. through focusing on worker-machine relationship (Boddy, 2008) p46. Mathematics and engineering have been used by Frank Gilbreth (1868–1924); who studied time- motion relationship, in order to decrease wastes and promote the efficiency of production process (Boddy, 2008) p48. Furthermore; Lillian Gilbreth (1878–1972), merged between psychology and management. She focused on the psychological aspect of management, through showing the essential need for rewarding workers in order to get the required results of scientific management (Boddy, 2008) p. 48. Moreover; “Mary Parker Follett (1868–1933)”; who merged sociology and psychology in management which formulate social psychology in order to demonstrate the importance of human relations in management which runs against the principles of scientific management (Boddy, 2008) p. 52. In addition; “Elton Mayo (1880–1949) the psychologist who focused also on the human relations through merging the psychology with management, in his famous experiment in western electric company (Boddy, 2008) p. 56. Moreover, Gareth Morgan in his book "Images of the Organization" (Gareth,1997); identified eight metaphors of organization, which brought out eight mergers between the management and various science. For example: Morgan saw organization as a machine (engineering and management); organization as psychic prison (psychology and management); organization as an organism (biology and management); organization as a brain (neuroscience and management). In addition; The field of organizational behavior have been founded since 1940s, when the researchers in sociology, economics, political science, psychology and other different social science integrated their efforts together to develop a huge body of organizational knowledge

(Wanger and Hollenbeck, 2010), p.5. (Johns, G. and Sacks, M., A., 2011), p. 6

Based on the above, the present research aims to enrich the literature in the area of management in general and in the field of organizational behavior (hereinafter OB) in specific, by adding a brick to the foundation of organizational cognitive neuroscience (hereinafter OCN) that was established by the previous researchers in the field of organizational behavior (OB), through studying neuro linguistic programming (hereinafter NLP) skills as a communication tool in the field of organizational behavior.

Although the novelty of NLP in the research area of OB concerning OCN approach, people and companies have become aware of the importance of NLP and its significant positive impact on the performance of individuals and organizations (Hejase and Hashem, 2015). NLP is seen as the science and art of excellence (Maisenbacher, 2013). Despite the research studies that showed the succession role of NLP in communication, in contrast; there are research studies criticized its role (Wake, 2011; Witkowski, 2012; Ahmadian, 2018). The abbreviated word “NLP” in Google search harvests approximately 16 million results. The holistic word” neuro linguistic programming” yields more than 695000 hits. These numbers reflect the interest of the prevalent/ diffuse worldwide in NLP in many fields (sport, education, police, Psychotherapy...etc.) (Witkowski, 2012). Although; individuals and organizations in business are aware of the NLP and its tangible positive effect on individual and company’s performance, NLP in the field of management is not popular, and still a recent concept. Based on the study of Hejase (2015), research studies in the area of business that is focusing on the study of NLP in the Middle Eastern region is not rare and not comprehensive.

2. Theoretical Background

The following titles and paragraphs highlight the theoretical background of the study concerning the study theories and Neuro Linguistic Programming in organization.

2.1 Organizational Behavior (hereinafter OB) and Organizational Cognitive Neuroscience (hereinafter OCN)

The roots of field of organizational behavior has been founded since 1940s, when the researchers in sociology, economics, political science, psychology and other different social science integrated their efforts together to develop a huge body of organizational knowledge (Wanger and Hollenbeck, 2010), p.5. Mickan and Boyce, (2007), defined OB as the way of realizing the degree to which employees behave and work in organizations, either in individuals' level or in a team. Furthermore; they indicated that the field of organizational behavior is derived from other fields, such as; sociology and psychology. The field of OB attempts to address the changes of human and organizational behavior as it happens in the context of the organization (Wanger and Hollenbeck, 2010), p.5. OB has been defined as the conceptual analysis of the way that employees behave inside organizations. (Leipzig and More, 1982). Based on the definition of (Johns and Sacks, 2011), p. 6. OB is the field in management that is interested in studying the individual's attitude and behavior and provide insight about how to manage and change the attitude and the behavior of individuals inside organization in order to get the desired outcomes. They also stated that organizational behavior as a field in management has three goals, namely: predict, explain and manage the individual behavior Johns and Sacks (2011), p.9. According to Turkalj and Fosić, (2009), OB is a study of a regular and systematic

behaviors that people do within the organization. According to the evolution of organizational behavior in literature, which dates back to the 1940s, the following paragraphs highlight the most recent approaches discussed and studied in the field of organizational behavior, as follows; Based on the study of Ashkanasy and Humphrey, (2011). Recently; the research studies in the field of OB begin to highlight and address the role and the effect of human brain in organizational behavior, through demonstrating how human brain can affect and change the individual behavior. This new trend in management specially in the field of OB connects neuroscience with organizational behavior, which is called neuro organizational behavior, Stanton, Day and Welpe, (2010) p.291. According to Becker, Cropanzano and Sanfey, (2011), they discussed that how the study of human brain can provide a new perspective that enhance and contribute to the theories of OB. The authors stated that neuroscience (NS) has already used in many fields of social science, such as; neuroscience used in economics in order to investigate the individual behavior in making decisions. Moreover; neuroscience is used in marketing, to help in knowing the role of emotions in the choice of customers, the authors believe that organizational neuroscience (hereinafter ON) represents an absent piece of the puzzle. Based on the study of Lindebaum, (2016), the author used another term that is called organizational cognitive neuroscience (hereinafter OCN), the author considered both organizational neuroscience (hereinafter ON) and organizational cognitive neuroscience have the same meaning. On contrast; Butler and Senior, (2017), stated that ON and OCN are representing different approaches in addressing brain into organizational and management research. They examined that OCN is more specific than ON in context of neuroscience. OCN is not only concentrating on the brain activity in

organizational behavior, but also considering the social context, cognition, neural activity and brain structure. Furthermore; Cropanzano and Sanfey, (2011), discussed that while organizational behavior studies focus on an explicit attitude of individuals, the organizational neuroscience focuses on the implicit attitude of the individuals, they pointed to the importance of applying and investigating the role of the implicit empirical studies in work place and in organizational phenomena. Accordingly; the organizational neuroscience can be seen as a new level of analysis and new approach in the literature of organizational behavior (Becker, Cropanzano and Sanfey, 2011). Moreover; Butler and Senior, (2017) indicated that the fertile area of neuroscience has extended to include organizational behavior. Based on Bagozzi and Lee, (2017), presented a model that links brain, mind and behavior, the authors called it as a (the brain, mind, behavior link naïve model), the model simply explain the relationship between our brain, our mind and our behavior. It demonstrates that our physical brain role in our thoughts and feelings, which in turn affect our behavior. The author also indicated that there are clearly opportunities in organizational behavior research that neuroscience methods and concepts can address (Bagozzi and Lee, 2017). According to Leipzig, and More, (1982); stated that organizational behavior view communication as one of many factors that can affect organizational performance. And communication items have relationship with other organizational variables. Moreover; they addressed that; the area of organizational behavior consider communication as a process which interrelated with other process of organizational behavior. Based on the study of Turkalj and Fosić, (2009); they considered communication as the most important element in organizational behavior and has an essential role in organizational success.

2.2 Neuro Linguistic Programming (hereinafter NLP)

NLP is the science and art of excellence (Maisenbacher, 2013). Neuro linguistic programming (hereinafter NLP) was originated in the mid1970s by John Grinder and Richard Blander. Blander`s experience was in mathematics, he was then a student whereas Grinder`s experience was in linguistic, he was associate professor of linguistics at Santa Cruz university. Initially; their work aimed to investigate the internal and the external behaviors that affected the succeeded therapists and turned them more influential than others (Ahmadian, 2018). Blander and Grinder conducted linguistic analysis to therapists, in order to develop an effective therapeutic approach, which is called Meta model. Meta model basically emphasizes on distortion, generalizations and deletions (Beaver, 1989). Meta-model language is strategy that links language with experience. It demonstrates which our thoughts can be translated into words. Language that individual uses to connect with environment is divided into two structures; internal or deep structure and external or surface structure. Internal structure/ surface related to unconscious level in human mind. Teacher in order to influence students, he/she works on influencing internal structure and transform from surface structure to deep structure of language by using meta-model language (Kudliskis, 2014). According to Ahmadian, (2018); Meta model that “uses language to identify language” through deletion, generalization and distortion. Which occur when a person tries to turn an intended message into actual speech. According to Santos, Júnior and de Souza, (2018); Blander and Grinder`s study showed that, people learn/ communicate through one of the three RS or through combination of two of them, the representation systems (hereinafter RS) are named and classified based on the type of processing performed, as follows: visual,

auditory and Kinesthetic. Visual; represents things observations or the use of vision in creating the internal images, for instance; through seeing photos. Auditory; involves retrieve memories through listening to sound. Kinesthetic; involves emotion, touch which are known as internal sensation. The authors argued that, one uses all three systems continuously, and we can't label person with one type of these three types. They stated that, person change his/ her type according to his/ her emotional state or the environment

wherein the person exists in. and he called this type a predominance representation system PRS. The authors stated that; we can recognize the PRS type of the person through his/ her sensory predicates or verbal clues. Verbal clues refer to words/ phrases that person use to describe situation, which demonstrate the consciousness of person at that moment. The authors showed that verbal clues are very important in guiding effective communication.

Figure 1: Eye movement (clues) in VAK system. Source: Hejase and Hashem, (2015).

Neuro linguistic programming (hereinafter NLP) was defined by Tosey and Mathison, (2010) as "a new, contested approach to learning, individual development and communication". Tosey and Mathison stated that NLP approach is familiar in education sector. Based on the study of Turan, Kodaz and Turan, (2016), they defined the term neuro linguistic programming as follow; neuro: is neurological system which affect the individual's feeling, attitude and behavior. Linguistic: is the internal representation code, which facilitates sharing experience and communication among individuals. Programming; represents how individual translates their experiences in order to achieve the desired results. Furthermore;

the study of Turan, Kodaz and Turan, (2016) defined NLP as the person's internal communication (intra-personal communication), and with other people (inter-personal communication). It facilitates communication between people. They also stated that NLP enhances and facilitates communication. They demonstrated that; communication based on NLP is consisted of three levels, which are; matching, harmony, and calibration (distinguish differences). According to Ilyas, (2017); neuro linguistic programming is a group of techniques that gives information regarding persons, (neuro) how they think, (linguistic) how they communicate with themselves and with other people and (programming) how

this communication influences individual's behavior. Ilyas, (2017) also stated that people pursue NLP skills unintentionally in one way or other and apply NLP techniques without being aware of it. Communication is very essential for business excellence. Communication among individuals, stress management and negotiation are important for business excellence which can be accomplished successfully through using NLP. NLP is a technology of behavior which demonstrates what happens inside us (intrapersonal communication) and what going on when we interact with others (interpersonal communication) (Singh and Abraham, 2008). NLP has four pillars, such as: relationship, that is, friendly and harmony, Know what in the mind of person, Sensory discrimination, flexibility

of individual's behavior. Relationship (communication) is the most important aspect among these pillars (Turan, Kodaz and Turan, 2016). Our future is shaped based on our interpretation to what we have seen or heard in the past. NLP teaches us that our perception toward things, events or people, is distorted due to numerous filters which our observations passing through. NLP enhances decision making through enabling the individual to recognize those filters and provides techniques to eliminate distortion caused by those filters (Vaes, 2018). NLP techniques used in teaching individual how to reach his/ her goals effectively, through determining language, thinking and process of behavior (Turan, Kodaz and Turan, 2016).

Figure 2: NLP communication model. Source: Hejase, H.J. and Hashem, F, (2015)

According to Sharma, (2018); role modeling as a technique of NLP, the author stated that role modelling is a very effective and powerful technique that can change the individual's behavior successfully. Sharma demonstrated that individual's values and beliefs are the key drivers for his/ her thoughts which in turn influence his/ her emotions and finally affect his behavior. NLP includes of many

different techniques that are applied successfully in order to achieve desired outcomes. Manager and leader can use the following NLP techniques; anchoring, reframing, pacing and leading and rapport. **Reframing**; is used to change the individual's perception regarding particular situation through putting the situation's content in different frame. For example, the statement of "the glass is half

empty” which can be reframed to “the glass is half full”, accordingly changing the recipient’s perception regarding this message. Thus; NLP technique (reframing) is very important technique for managers, it enables them to be more effective in communication and positively influence employees` response and behavior (Joey and Yazdanifard., 2015). **Anchoring technique** is one of NLP techniques, it is defined as a process which connects an individual’s internal response with external stimuli (Krugman, Kirsch, Wickless, Milling, Golicz, and Toth, 1985). For example, when a person touches another individual’s shoulder, the other person unconsciously will smile. Managers can use this technique in changing how a person feels, from negative feeling to positive state through using anchoring techniques (Joey and Yazdanifard., 2015). **Rapport technique** is very useful skill and easy to learn. Rapport techniques allows an individual to communicate successfully with any kind of people through gaining their confidence and trust. it includes the process of mirroring, which is the matching and following the person`s posture, gesture, body language and breathing to generate a harmonious environment. However, the leader needs to know the main sensory perception of the employee, whether it is kinesthetic, visual or auditory. Each sensory perception needs distinctive types of rapport. For example, when the main sensory perception of employee is auditory, the manager or leader can use a phrase like “I hear you”; however, for employee`s visual sensory perception, the leader can use statement like “my vision is clear” (Joey and Yazdanifard., 2015). **Pacing/ leading;** is NLP technique, which influences the managers` and leaders` communication skills. First; build trust with employees using pacing works through demonstrating understanding and respecting towards them, for instance; the choice of word shows understanding, appreciation and respect of the employee’s point of view.

Also; body language can support creating a harmonious environment. Accordingly; Effective pacing will enable and help the manager and leader to influence and lead employee (Joey and Yazdanifard., 2015)

2.3 Neuro Linguistic Programming (hereinafter NLP) Skills as A Communication Tool in The Workplace

NLP is important for enhancing a various psychological outcome in the workplace such as: occupational stress and self-esteem (Kotera, et al., 2019). The study of Elsherif, Ali, Ahmed, Amer and Mohamed, (2008); examined that organizations need to determine the NLP techniques that internal auditors use in order to enhance their performance. The study stated that; the predominant pattern on the performance of internal auditors is the NLP auditory style. While most of the procedures of the internal audit process are dominated by the visual pattern. According to Hassan and Mohamed, (2012); conducted NLP training program as intervention method, the contents of the training course sessions were; professional anchoring; inter-personal communication skills, inter- personal communication skills and professional experience. The authors measured the participants` skills, after and before Applying intervention program. the results showed that; the existence of a positive relationship with statistical significance between the application of the theory of NLP from the perspective of individual service and the development of the professional culture of social specialists in the field of care of youth, which confirms that the application of the NLP program of occupational intervention led to the development of the professional culture of social specialists with knowledge of concepts, information, values and facts related to the nature of work in the area Care of youth with a focus on utilization of all of this in the process of practice, and its reflection on the level of professional performance of

practitioners and social workers in the light of theories of NLP. Effective communication is considered the heart of organizational success. The manager or leader who has communication skills can lead the employees effectively. Neuro linguistic programming skills are essential for an exceptional manager specially in achieving win-win situation in negotiation, problem solving, stress management, influencing skills, persuasive, conflict resolving and individual development. NLP skills enhance and improved the manager's leadership skills and soft skills (Joey and Yazdanifard, 2015). The study of Maisenbacher, (2013); investigated the role of NLP as a tool of communication (in-terms of interpersonal which represented through the communication among stakeholders with each other and intrapersonal communication which existed in manager's mind) in enhancing communication in business. Intrapersonal communication shapes the quality of our communications. The author asserted that NLP can successfully facilitate communication and enhance the flexibility and problem solving in the workplace. Manager who uses neuro linguistic programming principles and skills can manage his business effectively and successfully. Furthermore; manager can loyalty and trust among employees. Thus; the management should concentrate their efforts on building relationships with the staff by using NLP techniques like; stress management and meta-programs and pursuit NLP skills such as; interpersonal communication skills (Singh and Abraham, 2008). Moreover, Yemm, (2006) stated that; the organization should provide NLP skills training for the employees. NLP training helps the employee to develop and improve his self-management, self-awareness and (intra-personal and inter-personal) communication skills. It can also help staff to build effective and positive relationship between customers and peers through improving their emotional intelligence.

Interpersonal communication skills are the ability of transmission meaning verbally or non- verbally from one to another or to many people (Matin, Jandaghi, Karimi and Hamidizadeh, 2010; Suhaimi, Marzuki and Mustaffa, 2014). Furthermore; the study of Ibrahim and Saleh, (2016); stated that, inter-personal communication skills of person are represented in problem solving (flexibility), representation systems and human relations (rapport). Whereas; intra-personal communication skills of person are the ability of person to communicate with himself by himself (Graeme and Dimpleby, 2006), through his thinking, beliefs and perception (Ibrahim and Saleh, 2016). According to Thompso, Courtney and Dickson, (2002); NLP is a group of distinctive techniques originated to improve individual's life. NLP helps one to better understand oneself and others and teaches him/ her how to build better communication with oneself and with others in order to enhance the relationship among people. The author conducted training course of NLP skills on staff and managers in the industry of hospitality in order to measure their performance before and after the intervention of training, in terms of: self- efficacy; self- steam; organizational commitment and adaptive selling. The results revealed that all three dimensions of individual performance were increased after the intervention of NLP training, but. Self-efficacy does not. The study indicated that NLP skills training in terms of communication skills don't affect individual self- efficacy. These results contrasted with the findings which indicated that, communication skills enhance individual self- efficacy in clinical context (Ammertorp, Sabroe, Kofoed, and Mainz, 2007), and in education context (Skinner and Croft, 2009). Furthermore; According to the study of Skinner and Croft, (2009); the study aimed to use framework of NLP in order to enhance the perception of self-efficacy regarding goal setting, motivation and time management to the undergraduate student. They applied

an exploratory study, dissertation workshop sessions for undergraduate. the session's module didn't focus on methodology but instead it focused on practical skills and soft skills (time management, motivation and goal setting). The techniques which used in the study were; focus group and semi-structured interview. The findings of the study shown that; the students who participated in workshop session were enhanced their perception regarding their self-efficacy (time management, motivation and goal setting) and their abilities, the intervention of NLP role should be used in order to enhance the low efficacious students' perception regarding their abilities and their self-efficacy, finally; The study stated that un-traditional students' self-efficacy doesn't rely on what skills they have, but instead it relies on their positive perception regarding their skills. Applying NLP techniques can improve the organizational culture and help the organization to achieve customer satisfaction and in turn gain competitive advantage as well as successful company and successful employees (Joey and Yazdanifard, 2015). The study of Scott, Lundgren and Thompson, (2018); indicated that, neuro linguistic programming is considered as a successful approach to organizational change. They asserted that applying NLP in supply chain management (hereinafter SCM) can enhance and improved negotiation and relation through effective communication. In their study they relied on the O'Conner's model which is named interpersonal communication model, that use in the negotiation context. This model consists of six levels as follows; environment (the when and where); beliefs (the why); capability (the how); behavior (the what); identity (the who); beyond identity (the connection). The negotiation conducted at each of these six levels through building rapport with the other party of negotiation. Finally; they summarized that applying different NLP connections build a trust through

negotiation cycle. Wake, (2011); the author demonstrated the difficulty and unfamiliarity of jargon of NLP in the workplace. The organization development consists of different stages, NLP techniques and tools inappropriate in this context. However; the study of Huczynski, (1993); the researcher conducted a historical analysis regarding the ideas of management such as: bureaucracy, scientific management, classical management, human relations, and neo-human relations. The researcher examines the relationship between the manager who is looking for a means of change in the management and his consultants as the relationship between the consumer and the supplier. The manager represents the consumer who is looking for new management ideas. The consultant represents the seller or supplier who sells such ideas. The manager seeks for buying programs, company's development intervention, training courses and organization's change programs, for many reasons, such as; new technique can be used to solve critical problem in the organization, new ideas can influence the internal motivation, new ideas can generate innovative solutions for the continuing problems. The author argued that, new change in management needs new techniques in solving problems, he demonstrated that, this doesn't mean that traditional or old approaches are useless or incorrect, he argued that these approaches are boring, accordingly; recently, managers are looking for new answer/reply for an old question which doesn't rely on old explanation. The author categorized intervention techniques and programs which be used by managers in order to make change in management, into two categories, namely; A and B. Category (A) represents traditional techniques such as; management by objectives (MBO), quality circles and job enrichment. And category (B) represents new intervention ideas and new age training courses such as; neuro linguistic programming (NLP).

The author argued that, traditional/ old techniques became common property to large percentage of organization, instead new age training course such as NLP still new ideas as a means in changing management, which means that applied NLP can help organization to achieve competitive advantage than rivals who don't apply it. NLP can improve and enhance the individual's perception and achievement and can influence the employees' motivation, success and communication skills (Taspinar, Semerci, Semerci and Guney 2007). Peker, (2010) conducted conceptual study which built on the notion of NLP concerning thinking and reprogramming strategies. The study supported the claim of NLP theorists regarding our ability to change and reprogram our structure of thought in order to achieve a potential successor point. The study stated that the neurological process of human's five senses are building blocks of individual's experience, that is why this is called our structures of thought, which can be demonstrated in terms of how we think through using our nervous system. The author explained that there are three types of thinking. Thinking process in terms of VAK model in NLP. He explained that visual thinker people tend to think about their visual experience, they remembered the images. Auditory people, (auditory thinker) think about sounds, and kinesthetic thinker who think in terms of feeling. The paper created attention to the term "Reprogramming". By influencing the behavior patterns of individual through influencing his thought structures. The author defined programming as the behavior patterns that were derived from our structure of our thoughts (experience). Therefore; in order to change these patterns of behavior, we should change our

thoughts re-structure (reprogramming). From this point of view, we can say that NLP provides a variety of strategies and techniques that we can use in re-programming ourselves thoughts and in turn our behavior pattern. Based on the study of Jemmer, (2006); NLP techniques that are used in changing one's beliefs, values, attitude and behavior, are not rigid steps or procedures that are working under only rigorously conditions. Jemmer stated that, beliefs are shaped what will happen in the future, the author demonstrated that our past experience, beliefs and values can be reframed, reprogramed (changed) in order to design and get better future. The reframing and reprogramming concepts are based on the notion that our beliefs and values can be changed over time; they are not fixed. Change beliefs and values will lead to change the individual attitude and in turn change the behavior (Jemmer, 2006). According to the study of Ashok and Santhakumar, (2002), NLP training can enhance both organizational performance and individual performance. Ashok and Santhakumar, demonstrated the significant of NLP in TQM. The authors asserted that using NLP in organization can improve individual's performance. They compared between using NLP training and not using it on the performance of individuals regarding kaizen and 5s that identified as tools for lateral thinking. The results showed that; NLP training is an effective thinking tool in improving the performance of both; the organization and individuals simultaneously. They also asserted that; recently, the TQM approach has changed and evolved to focus on individual development in order to achieve the organization's success.

Figure 3: The company growth with and without using NLP. Ashok and Santhakumar, (2002)

NLP can facilitate the relationship between leaders and subordinates in the workplace through a representation system (Hejase and Hashem, 2015). Furthermore; Mehrabian, (2017), set the 7%, 38%, 58% rule which indicates that non- verbal communication influence 93% of communication in workplace.

Figure 4: Rapport as NLP technique effect in our communication (7, 38, 58 rule). Source: Mehrabian, (2017)

3. Research Problem; Significance

In literature, the abbreviated word “NLP” in Google search harvests approximately 16 million results. The holistic word” neuro linguistic programming” yields more than 695000 hits. These numbers reflect the interest of the prevalent/ diffuse worldwide in NLP in many fields ((sport, law, police, psychology, language teaching and learning) (Bashir and Ghani, 2012; Witkowski, 2012). However; NLP in the area of management is not popular, and still a recent concept. Although; individuals and organizations in business

are aware of the NLP and its tangible positive effect on individual and company’s performance. Based on the study of Hejase (2015), research studies in the area of business that is focusing on the study of NLP in the Middle Eastern region is not rare and not comprehensive. There are few studies that have studied NLP in the field of management, especially in the area of organizational behavior. Additionally; among these few studies, there is a discrepancy between their findings regarding the importance of NLP and its impact (Witkowski, 2012) in workplace and on managerial concepts in

the field of management in general, and in organizational behavior in particular.

Based on the above, the current research contributes to the literature of OB, as follows; First; the current research enriches the literature by adding a brick to the foundation of organizational cognitive neuroscience (OCN) that is established by the previous researchers in the area of OB by merging two different sciences: Neuropsychology science and management science which is represented by Organizational behavior, and formulate new science which is called organizational cognitive neuroscience (OCN) (Lindebaum, 2016). Neuropsychology is the science that is founded by Freud, who discover the brain- the human behavior relationship (Eric and Mary, 2008). Furthermore; it conceptually adds to the active debate on the applicability of NLP as an effective communication tool that can improve the communication and individual behavior in workplace.

4. Research Objective; Question

The main objective of the present study is to investigate the importance of using NLP skills as a communication tool in the workplace. To do so, the current research is directed toward answering the core research question which is: "Do Neuro Linguistic Programming skills as a communication tool, important in the workplace?"

5. Research Methodology

The current study is classified as an exploratory study in order to explore new / un-familiar NLP field in the management research, and obtain deep insight regarding the field of the study which will help the researcher in developing the research hypotheses and developing the proposed research model. The researcher applies an exploratory study, relying on two qualitative methods, in order to explore the importance of NLP skills as a

communication tool in management in general and in workplace in specific, through conducting the following methods: The first, is concentrating in reviewing literature regarding NLP skills in the field of management concerning the area of organizational behavior. The second method, is conducting semi-structured interviews with seven NLP practitioners/ experts who have a background in business, from different regions in the world, in order to investigate the importance of NLP in management in general and in workplace in particular. Concerning The first method is reviewing literature: in order to find the research gap in literature in the field of management concerning NLP as a recent approach of communication in literature, the researcher began reviewing literature from 2016 till 2019. She reviewed periodical articles; published and un-published dissertations; books; research papers; papers which is published in international conferences; academic journals. As a result of reviewing literature; the researcher noticed shortage of studies in the area of management concerning NLP as a communication tool, and among these few studies, there is a debate among researchers regarding the effectiveness of NLP in management. The second method; is conducting semi- structured interviews with seven experts, certified NLP practitioners who have business background, from different regions in the world. The researcher needed to know more from the experts in the field of NLP. Thus; the researcher asked the experts questions concerning the importance and the effectiveness of NLP in management. The questions developed from literature. According to the technique that was used by the researcher; due to most participants live in other countries, so it is difficult for the researcher to conduct face-to-face interviews, this resulting in the use of other techniques. The researcher communicated with participants through using telephone; e- mail; social media

video chatting (in order to see the body language of the participants when he answers the questions). The researcher recorded the qualitative data (responses of participants) then analyzed them through comparing them with each other in order to give a conclusion of the exploratory

study. During interviews discussions and after analyzing the collected qualitative data, the researcher summarized the opinion of the seven participants regarding questions in order to get the final answer regarding the research question.

Table 1: Interview`s Questions

Questions	Source
<p>Do NLP skills as a communication tool enhance the communication in the workplace?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tell me which NLP skills can be used in workplace, especially in educational management? ▪ Do NLP skills promote communication in the workplace, such as between teaching staff and students in universities? ▪ NLP skills can be used externally - communicating with others in the workplace or internally - communicating within ourselves at the workplace? ▪ Do NLP skills improve the external communication with others in the workplace? ▪ Do NLP skills enhance internal communication within oneself (the teaching staff)? How? 	<p>Maisenbacher, (2013)</p>

6. Findings

After analyzing the interviewees` responses, the researcher can conclude the followings:

- NLP is extremely useful in business; sales; marketing; teambuilding; time management and all sort of applications
- NLP skills neuro linguistic programming skills are very important skills that management and employees can use are representational system, predicates, meta modal, anchoring, leading and pacing, sensory acuity, building rapport, understanding strategies of others,
- NLP is used externally - communicating with others in the workplace and communicating internally - within ourselves

- NLP promote communication in the workplace through using communication mechanisms through the building of familiarity and ways of persuasion in understanding the strategies and ways of thinking of others and the quality of their personalities
- NLP improve the external communication with others in the workplace, to a very large extent, using all the different communication mechanisms, from understanding the ways of thinking of the other, the hidden meaning behind his words and his actions, and also to achieve common goals in the work place
- All programming mechanisms help to understand the person deeply
- Companies that use NLP in communicating with customers achieve greater profits and excellent customer service

7. Conclusion

The present exploratory study aims to explore and investigate the importance of NLP skills as a communication tool in the workplace. To do so, the researcher conducted interviews with 7 NLP practitioners who have business background. The results support the significance of NLP skills as a communication tool in management in general and in the workplace in particular. Which opens the window for the future researchers to investigate various relationships among different managerial concepts focusing neuro-linguistic programming perspective.

8. References

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